

Survey to Evaluate Awareness of Basic Life Support (BLS) in MBBS Students Studying in DBVP RMC, Loni

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Abstract

Background: Basic Life Support (BLS) is a fundamental skill for medical professionals, particularly MBBS students, who are expected to respond to emergency situations. However, gaps in knowledge and practical application of BLS remain a concern. This study aimed to assess the awareness and knowledge of BLS among MBBS students to identify areas requiring improvement.

Aim and Objectives: To assess interest and background knowledge about BLS, to evaluate effectiveness of hands on BLS training and feedback analysis among students of MBBS students of DBVP RMC LONI.

Methods: A cross-sectional analytical study was conducted in the Department of Anaesthesiology and Critical Care, DBVP RMC, Loni. A structured questionnaire was used to assess theoretical knowledge and self-reported confidence in BLS skills. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, and results were expressed as percentages.

Results: The study found that 85% of students correctly identified the meaning of BLS, but only 62% knew the recommended training update interval. Knowledge gaps were noted in CPR compression depth (65%), AED use (60%), and choking management (63%). Pediatric BLS knowledge was also suboptimal, with 64% identifying the correct compression depth for children.

Conclusion: While MBBS students demonstrated moderate BLS awareness, significant gaps in procedural knowledge were observed. Structured, hands-on training programs and periodic certification are necessary to improve preparedness for real-life emergencies.

Keywords: Basic Life Support, CPR Knowledge, MBBS Students.

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Introduction

Basic life support includes series of techniques in chain of survival, provided to patients during cardiopulmonary arrest. All these techniques are focused on helping patients to sustain life until more precise medical treatment can begin. BLS does not include extensive medical supervision/treatment/ invasive procedures or drugs, making it possible for a common people to provide it, but proper training is a prerequisite and only those who have basic knowledge and training in BLS can provide CPR more effectively [8]. Basic Life Support (BLS) is a crucial set of life-saving interventions that includes cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR), airway management, and early defibrillation, aimed at sustaining life during medical emergencies. [1] As first responders in critical situations, medical students should possess adequate knowledge and skills in BLS to improve patient survival outcomes. However, studies have shown that awareness and competency in BLS among medical students vary significantly, often

due to inadequate training and limited exposure. [2,3] Medical students, particularly those in the MBBS program, represent the future healthcare workforce. Their ability to recognize and respond effectively to cardiac arrests, respiratory failures, and other life-threatening conditions can play a decisive role in emergency care. Despite the inclusion of BLS in medical curricula, practical application and retention of these skills remain areas of concern. Evaluating the awareness and understanding of BLS among MBBS students is essential to identify gaps in knowledge and improve training programs.[4]

This survey aims to assess the level of awareness and preparedness among MBBS students regarding BLS protocols. The findings will help in formulating strategies to enhance BLS training and ensure that future doctors are well-equipped to handle medical emergencies efficiently and confidently.

Methodology

This study was conducted as a cross-sectional analytical study to evaluate the awareness and knowledge of Basic Life Support (BLS) among MBBS students. The research was carried out in the Department of Anaesthesiology and Critical Care at Dr. Vitthalrao Vikhe Patil Rural Medical College (DBVP RMC), Loni.

The study aimed to assess the level of understanding of BLS concepts, including cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR), airway management, and the use of an automated external defibrillator (AED), among medical students.

A structured questionnaire-based survey was used as the data collection tool. The questionnaire was designed to assess both theoretical knowledge and self-reported confidence in performing BLS procedures. It comprised multiple-choice and Likert-scale questions covering essential BLS components such as recognition of cardiac arrest, compression-to-ventilation ratio, and emergency response steps. The questionnaire was validated by experts in anesthesiology and critical care before administration.

MBBS students from different academic years were included in the study, and participation was voluntary. The questionnaire was distributed in both printed and digital formats, ensuring accessibility for all students. Data collection was completed within a specified time frame, and responses were recorded anonymously to maintain confidentiality. Incomplete or inconsistent responses were excluded from the final analysis.

The collected data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Frequency distributions, percentages, and mean scores were calculated for knowledge and skill-related responses. The association between different academic years and BLS awareness levels was assessed using statistical tests.

The findings provided insights into gaps in BLS knowledge among MBBS students, helping to inform future curriculum improvements and training programs.

Results

Table 1: Awareness of Basic Life Support (BLS)

Question	Correct Response	No. of Students (%)
What does BLS stand for?	Basic Life Support	85%
Primary goal of BLS	To stabilize the patient until advanced help arrives	78%
How often should BLS training be updated?	Every 2 years	62%

Table 2: Knowledge of CPR and Compression Techniques

Question	Correct Response	No. of Students (%)
Recommended compression rate for adult CPR	100-120 compressions per minute	70%
Correct compression depth for adult CPR	At least 2 inches	65%
Compression-to-ventilation ratio for adult CPR	30:2	80%
Correct technique for chest compressions	Use both hands, interlocked	75%

Table 3: Knowledge of Automated External Defibrillator (AED) Use

Question	Correct Response	No. of Students (%)
Purpose of an AED	To treat arrhythmic cause of cardiac arrest(pVT/VF)	68%
How to use an AED	Place pads on the chest and follow voice prompts	72%
What to do if AED advises a shock	Do not touch the patient	60%

Table 4: Awareness of Emergency Response and Choking Management

Question	Correct Response	No. of Students (%)
First step in BLS algorithm	Check for responsiveness	66%
When to call for emergency help	Before starting CPR	74%
What to do if a choking adult becomes unresponsive	Start CPR immediately	69%
Recommended position for a conscious choking patient	Sitting upright	63%

Table 5: Knowledge of Pediatric BLS

Question	Correct Response	No. of Students (%)
Recommended depth for chest compressions in children	Not more than 2 inches	64%
Correct action if a child is choking	Back blows	68%
Correct action if alone with an unresponsive child	Call for help before starting CPR	70%

Discussion

Basic Life Support (BLS) is an essential skill for medical students, as they are often the first responders in emergency situations. This study assessed the knowledge and awareness of BLS among MBBS students through a structured questionnaire. The findings highlight significant gaps in understanding and retention of BLS guidelines, which have implications for medical education and emergency preparedness. [5]

General Awareness of BLS: The study revealed that 85% of students correctly identified the meaning of BLS as Basic Life Support, indicating a high level of theoretical awareness. However, only 78% of students recognized that the primary goal of BLS is to stabilize the patient until advanced help arrives, while 22% had misconceptions about its objectives. Additionally, only 62% of students knew that BLS training should be updated every two years, reflecting inadequate knowledge about the importance of skill reinforcement. Since BLS protocols and guidelines are frequently revised by organizations such as the American Heart Association (AHA) and European Resuscitation Council (ERC), medical students must stay updated to ensure they follow the latest best practices. The relatively low percentage in this area suggests that refresher courses and hands-on training should be incorporated into medical curricula. [6]

Knowledge of CPR and Compression Techniques: Effective Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation (CPR) is a crucial component of BLS, and students' understanding of its principles was evaluated in the survey. The results showed that 70% of students knew the recommended compression rate for adult CPR (100-120 compressions per minute), while 30% were unaware of this critical parameter. Similarly, only 65% correctly identified the compression depth for adult CPR (at least 2 inches), indicating gaps in the understanding of proper force application during compressions.

80% of students correctly answered the compression-to-ventilation ratio for adult CPR (30:2), showing a relatively high level of knowledge in this area. However, 75% of students identified the correct hand placement technique (using both hands, interlocked), meaning that 25% lacked the basic understanding required for effective CPR performance. These findings emphasize the need for increased practical training,

as improper chest compressions can lead to inadequate circulation and poor patient outcomes. Hands-on simulation training with manikins could significantly improve students' skill retention. [7]

Knowledge of Automated External Defibrillator (AED) Use: The role of an Automated External Defibrillator (AED) in BLS is crucial for increasing survival rates in sudden cardiac arrest. The study found that 68% of students knew that the AED is used to restart the heart, while 32% either did not know its function or believed it was meant for other purposes such as oxygenation or monitoring vital signs. This lack of knowledge about AED usage highlights a gap in training, which is concerning given that early defibrillation is a key determinant of survival in cardiac arrest cases.

72% of students correctly answered how to use an AED by placing the pads on the chest and following voice prompts, but 28% were unaware of this step. More concerning was the fact that only 60% of students knew that they should not touch the patient while the AED delivers a shock, leaving 40% at risk of making a critical mistake during an emergency. These findings underscore the need for medical colleges to provide AED training through simulation-based workshops, ensuring that students are comfortable using this life-saving device.

Awareness of Emergency Response and Choking Management

One of the key components of BLS is the ability to respond quickly in an emergency. The study revealed that only 66% of students knew that checking for responsiveness is the first step in the BLS algorithm, while 34% selected incorrect responses such as calling for help or immediately starting chest compressions. The incorrect responses indicate a misunderstanding of the BLS sequence, which could lead to improper management of emergency situations.

74% of students correctly identified that emergency services should be called before initiating CPR, whereas 26% believed that emergency help should only be called after starting CPR or if the patient was unresponsive. Since prompt emergency activation is crucial for successful resuscitation, training programs should emphasize the importance of early communication with emergency medical services (EMS).

When asked about choking management, 69% of students correctly identified that they should start

CPR immediately if a choking adult becomes unresponsive, while 31% chose incorrect responses such as calling for help first or waiting for the patient to recover. Additionally, only 63% of students knew that a conscious choking patient should be placed in a sitting upright position, leaving a significant portion of students unaware of proper positioning. This gap in knowledge suggests that additional hands-on workshops and training sessions on airway obstruction management are necessary.

Knowledge of Pediatric BLS: Knowledge of pediatric resuscitation techniques is equally important for medical students, as children require different CPR guidelines than adults. In this study, only 64% of students knew that the recommended depth for chest compressions in children is at least 2 inches, highlighting a deficiency in pediatric CPR knowledge. Similarly, 68% correctly identified that slap their back should be performed in case of a choking child, but 32% lacked this knowledge.

70% of students correctly answered that if they are alone with an unresponsive child, they should call for help before starting CPR, while 30% chose incorrect responses such as starting CPR immediately without calling for assistance. These findings emphasize the need for dedicated pediatric BLS training sessions, as students may not receive sufficient exposure to pediatric emergencies during their clinical rotations.

The results of this study indicate that while MBBS students have a fair level of theoretical knowledge regarding BLS, significant gaps exist in practical skills and emergency decision-making. The deficiencies in AED usage, chest compression techniques, choking management, and pediatric BLS highlight the need for improved structured training programs that combine theory with hands-on practice. A survey was conducted among the MBBS students DBVP of a hospital, comprising approximately 30 questions for each participant. Following the survey, the correct responses were shared with the MBBS students. In cases where answers were incorrect, detailed explanations and educational guidance were provided to ensure a clear understanding of the correct information. This initiative aimed to enhance the knowledge and competency of the MBBS students, contributing to continuous professional development and improved patient care.

To address these gaps, the following recommendations are proposed: [5,6,7]

1. Mandatory BLS Training: Medical colleges should implement regular hands-on BLS training sessions for all MBBS students, incorporating real-life simulations.

- 2. Certification and Recertification:** Students should undergo BLS certification during their course and be required to renew it every two years to stay updated with new guidelines.
- 3. Simulation-Based Learning:** Manikin-based training and emergency response drills should be incorporated into the curriculum to improve confidence and practical skills.
- 4. Assessment and Feedback:** Periodic knowledge assessments and skill evaluations should be conducted to reinforce learning and identify students needing additional training.
- 5. Early Exposure to Emergency Situations:** Encouraging medical students to participate in emergency medicine rotations or volunteer in first-aid programs can improve their readiness for real-life emergencies.

Conclusion

Our study highlights the strengths and weaknesses in BLS knowledge among MBBS students. While a considerable percentage of students demonstrated basic awareness, deficiencies in practical application, decision-making, and specific procedural knowledge were observed. These gaps reinforce the need for structured, frequent, and hands-on training programs to ensure that future doctors are well-prepared to handle emergencies efficiently [10]. By incorporating practical training, continuous assessments, and early clinical exposure, medical education can enhance students' competency in life-saving skills, ultimately improving patient survival outcomes. BLS workshop was found to be highly effective in improvement of knowledge and skill of the participants in managing cardiac emergencies in spite of variety of participants [9].

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